

EFFECT OF CONTEXTUALIZED-BASED E-LEARNING MODULES IN CHEMISTRY 10 ON STUDENT'S CONCEPTUAL UNDERSTANDING

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Effect of Contextualized-Based E-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10 on Student's Conceptual Understanding

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Abstract

This study was undertaken to develop and validate Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10 of Sta. Elena High School, City Schools Division of Marikina City, School Year 2022-2023. The researcher used descriptive research design in the study to evaluate the developed Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10, and to assess the level of performance of the student respondents after the utilization of the mentioned material. The sources of data were the twenty (20) experts and twenty (20) Science teachers, as well as thirty (30) Grade 10 students. The teacher-respondents evaluated the material as Very Satisfactory with a grand weighted mean of 3.86 and 3.88 respectively and showed no significant difference. Meanwhile, the performance of the students as reflected in their pre-test and post-test results showed substantial increase from 62.50% to 90.60% and indicated significant difference. Furthermore, the respondents commended the aid that the e-learning module to learners as it contains informative content, while they suggested to further improve some of its parts for clearer instructions.

Keywords: *e-learning module, contextualized, Chemistry, conceptual, performance*

Introduction

Distance education involves educators guiding students through their learning journey using online platforms or modular resources, with the teacher and students being physically separated. In the Philippines, The COVID-19 pandemic greatly affected education, leading to the use of online learning methods from 2020 to 2022.

Within a constrained timeframe following the onset of the pandemic, numerous researchers have shared their ideas and efforts regarding education and learning using various approaches. Traditional in-person teaching has been phased out gradually across many educational institutions, spanning from schools to colleges and universities. The current imperative is to formulate and apply novel methods for teaching and evaluating learning (Pokhrel et al., 2021).

The Department of Education (DepEd) issued DepEd Order No. 18 series 2020, titled "Policy Guidelines for the Provision of Learning Resources in the Implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP)." This policy indicates that the Department of Education (DepEd) has the authority to furnish learning materials as part of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan. To address the difficulties brought about by COVID-19, DepEd must be inventive and resourceful in delivering education that is of high quality, easily accessible, relevant, and empowering. The BE-LCP ensures that learners receive safe and secure learning opportunities through various methods. To make this happen, the Department is urgently creating, producing, and supplying learning resources through its Regional and School Division Offices.

According to the constitution, Executive Order No. 292 under the Administrative Code of 1987, Republic Act No. 9155 (Governance of Basic Education Act of 2001), and RA 10533 (Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013), the Department of Education (DepEd) is mandated by law to uphold and advance the right to a high-quality basic education. Consequently, DepEd is required by law to offer a K-12 basic education program that is learner-centered, comprehensive, flexible, relevant, and personalized.

In accordance with its legal responsibilities, the Department of Education (DepEd) has released guidelines regarding flexible learning and educational materials. Notably, DepEd Order No. (DO) 21, series 2019, and the Policy Guidelines for the K-12 Basic Education Program serve as examples of this commitment. These directives introduce Flexible Learning Options (FLOs), which include alternative methods of delivering education and corresponding resources designed to meet the diverse needs, backgrounds, and variations of learners.

This indicates that the policy guidelines intend to set standards and criteria for furnishing learning resources during the implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BE-LCP). These learning resources serve as comprehensive toolkits for learners, encompassing protocols, guidelines, and additional information designed to enhance the learning process. Responsible adults must supervise the learning process, with teachers offering ongoing monitoring and guidance to ensure effective education.

The researcher's objective includes the development of Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry tailored for Grade 10 students, intended for their utilization in the science curriculum. If distance learning is reintroduced, the researcher aims to offer students the opportunity to develop critical thinking abilities, essential skills, and core values within the realm of learning Chemistry. Additionally, the researcher has developed a module designed to facilitate students' comprehension and practical application of scientific knowledge, both within their local environment and on a global scale whenever feasible. This module will also guide students in carrying out scientific procedures and honing related skills, while fostering the cultivation and display of scientific mindsets and principles.

Consequently, the research objective is to formulate e-Learning modules for Chemistry that are Contextualized Based and can be customized and implemented by educators. The rationale behind crafting Contextualized -Based e-Learning modules is threefold: 1) Students exhibit enhanced learning outcomes when immersed in practical, real-world scenarios, 2) It will offer engaging tasks that students can connect with to enhance their comprehension and render the concepts more relatable., 3) It will furnish students with extra sets of problems and illustrative instances, aiding in their retention of the lesson.

In these, the researcher decided to create and test Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry for Grade 10 students. Because for her the availability of enhanced and easily accessible learning materials can serve as a motivation for students to engage in study, particularly in cases where distance learning is reintroduced. Moreover, these resources can play a crucial role in aiding students' grasp of the essential concepts in Chemistry 10, which will subsequently act as a foundation for their academic journey in Senior High School. The researcher holds the belief that possessing a strong fundamental understanding of Chemistry will facilitate a faster and smoother acquisition of knowledge and comprehension of the subject and its lessons.

Research Questions

This study aimed to develop and evaluate Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10 at Sta. Elena High School the Division of Marikina City for S.Y 2022-2023. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What were the five most important topics in Chemistry that were developed into Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10 based on the K to 12 curriculum as perceived by the Science Teachers?
2. What was the evaluation of the science teachers and science experts on the developed Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10 in terms of the following:
 - a) content quality;
 - b) instructional quality;
 - c) technical quality; and
 - d) accuracy and up-to-datedness?
3. Was there a significant difference in the evaluation of the two groups of respondents on the developed Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10 based on the above-mentioned criteria?
4. What was the level of Conceptual understanding of Grade 10 students before and after using the Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10?
5. Was there a significant difference in the mean score of the Grade 10 students in the pretest and posttest?
6. What were the comments and suggestions of the teachers and experts to improve the Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10?

Literature Review

Contextualization refers to the practice of connecting appropriate information and instructional methods to learners (DepEd, 2016). It involves using things, events, and experiences that are meaningful and relevant to students when presenting and discussing learning material.

Compared to the conventional method of teaching and learning, contextual teaching and learning can enable students to learn more, put to use what they learn, and enjoy the process of learning. It also enables the teachers to improve their students' engagement, as well as enhance their relationship with their students. Contextual teaching considers the experiences and interests of the students in order to ensure that these students can relate to what is being taught to them. Unlike conventional teaching, it only requires the students to learn through memorization or rote learning (Agarwal, 2019).

In Science, contextual learning has influenced the process of teaching and learning for the individuals that are involved in learning Science. Sevian et al. (2018) presents in their study about what is already known about context-based learning (CBL) and what is yet to be learned about CBL. They emphasize in their study that students who learn chemistry often have a lot of difficulties in the current learning process because of multiple reasons. For this reason, contextual teaching is the best process for chemistry students. This is because it guarantees that the students learn from situations that they can relate and use for later on, as well as get hands-on experience regarding what they learn.

Moreover, Suryawati and Osman (2017) mentioned in their study that contextual learning also gives students the opportunity to learn more because they are enabled to construct an experience that can give them further knowledge about what they are learning. The researchers also mention that science learning is often involved with contextual learning because there is a need to understand scientific procedures, the existence of substances, and the phenomena regarding scientific occurrences and substances. It can also enhance the critical thinking skills of students which is needed in the scientific strand. Through contextual based learning in Science, it can also improve the problem solving and inquiry skills of the students.

Also, according to Majid and Rohaeti (2018), context-based Chemistry learning is very effective for the students as it improves their sense of achievement and attitude. This statement is also backed up by the results of their study wherein it showed that there is a relationship in the type of learning method and the sense of student achievement and attitude of the students.

Furthermore, Armstrong and Poe (2020) also highlight in their study that there is a need to ensure that chemistry students have the know-how and hands-on experience about what they are learning. Through contextualized learning, they can have a firsthand experience of the theories they are learning. In addition to this, it requires them to work in groups and have an interaction with what they are learning about. Ultimately, the study showed that contextualized learning is very impactful in the learning process of the students, especially in subjects that relate to science.

The gathered studies and literature showed that Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10 can help improve the learning process of the Chemistry students as well as the experience and sense of achievement and attitude of the students. With this, it can guide the proponents of the study about the Effects of Contextualized Based e-Learning on the student's conceptual understanding in Chemistry 10.

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher employed the descriptive method as the research approach. As per Bluman (2012), descriptive research involves gathering, organizing, summarizing, and presenting data.

As stated by Smith (2018), descriptive research aims to portray the characteristics of a phenomenon or population accurately, offering an in-depth snapshot without altering variables. It relies on quantitative methods like surveys or observations to collect data, which are then analyzed using statistical measures such as frequencies, percentages, or averages. This approach provides a comprehensive overview of the existing situation without delving into causal relationships between variables.

Participants

There are two sets of participants. The initial group comprises 20 Science teachers and 20 Science experts in various schools who will serve as evaluators of the contextual learning materials in terms of content quality instructional quality, technical quality, and accuracy up-to-datedness. One class from the grade 10 level was used as the source of data for the validation of the Developed Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10. Pretest and posttest were used to validate the instructional materials.

Instruments

In this study, the researcher employed a questionnaire checklist derived from the Evaluation Tool Content of the Department of Education (DepEd) for assessing the Contextualized Instructional Module in Chemistry for Grade 10. This tool was utilized to collect evaluations from both science teachers and science experts regarding the Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10. The pretest and posttest were employed to collect data on the performance of Grade 10 students before and after the instruction using the Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10.

Procedure

The researcher provided a survey questionnaire to the science teachers for the top five important topics to be developed into Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10 based on their perception.

Following the creation of the Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10, the researcher provided a copy to the respondents for evaluation. To collect the required information, the researcher sought permission from the School Head of Sta. Elena High School to administer the questionnaire to the designated respondents. Upon receiving approval, the researcher distributed the learning modules to the respondents and conducted the administration and retrieval of the survey questionnaire from both science teacher and science expert respondents. A total of 20 Science experts and 20 Science teachers from Sta. Elena High School and other schools evaluated the Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10. The Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10 were tried out for Grade 10 students to determine their effectiveness.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher herself explained and gave the informed consent to each participant before the conduct of the study. She ensured them that the information would be used with utmost confidentiality and within the purpose of the study only.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings according to the study's research questions.

Topics in Chemistry that were Developed into Contextualized e-Learning Modules Based on the Perception of the Science Teachers

The identified five (5) topics based on the teacher's perception survey were: 1) Gas Law; 2) Major Categories of Biomolecules; 3) Chemical Reaction; 4) Balancing of Chemical Equation; 5) Factors Affecting Chemical Reaction. These topics were developed into Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10.

Table 1. *Perceived Topics in Chemistry by Science Teachers*

Module Number	Topics	Percentage	Rank
1	Gas Law Variable of gas, Kinetic Molecular Theory, Boyle's Law, and Charles' Law	74%	5
2	Major Categories of Biomolecules Carbohydrates, Protein, Lipids, Nucleic Acid	79%	3.5
3	Chemical Reaction Combination, Decomposition, Single-Displacement Reaction, Double-Displacement Reaction	89%	2
4	Balancing of Chemical Equation	95%	1
5	Factors Affecting Chemical Reaction	79%	3.5

This suggests that the five specified topics within the Grade 10 Chemistry curriculum have been recognized as important lessons that students at this level should prioritize studying and fully grasp. Furthermore, it underscores the necessity for these topics to receive concentrated focus to effectively deepen students' comprehension and proficiency in Chemistry.

Evaluation of the Experts and the Teachers on the Developed Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10

Table 2. *Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10 as to Content Quality*

	Content Quality	Respondents			
		Teachers		Experts	
		WM	VI	WM	VI
1.	Content is consistent with topics/skills found in the DepEd Learning Competencies for the subject and grade/year level it was intended.	3.90	VS	3.80	VS
2.	Concepts developed contribute to enrichment, reinforcement, or mastery of the identified learning objectives.	3.90	VS	3.95	VS
3.	Content is accurate.	3.95	VS	3.80	VS
4.	Content is up-to-date.	4.00	VS	3.95	VS
5.	Content is logically developed and organized.	4.00	VS	3.95	VS
6.	Content is free from cultural, gender, racial, or ethics bias.	3.90	VS	3.85	VS
7.	Content stimulates and promotes critical thinking.	3.81	VS	3.95	VS
8.	Content is relevant to real-life situations.	3.95	VS	3.95	VS
9.	Language (including vocabulary) is appropriate to the target user level.	4.00	VS	3.95	VS
10.	Content promotes positive values that support formative growth.	3.90	VS	3.95	VS
Overall Weighted Mean		3.93	VS	3.91	VS

Table 2 shows that the Science teachers achieved a weighted mean of 3.93, and the experts attained a score of 3.91, accompanied by standard deviations of 0.15 and 0.23, respectively. These values are verbally interpreted as Very Satisfactory.

This means that the content quality of the contextualized-based e-learning modules in Chemistry 10 aligns with the DepEd Learning Competencies, ensuring consistency with topics and skills. These modules contribute to the enrichment, reinforcement, or mastery of specified learning objectives. The content is accurate, up-to-date, logically developed, and well-organized. It is free from cultural, gender, racial, or ethical bias, fostering an inclusive learning environment.

The results of our study align closely with the research conducted by Pinuela (2022). In the study conducted by Pinuela, it was revealed that the participants expressed very satisfaction with respect to the quality of content in the digitalized work activities for Science 10 (Chemistry).

Table 3. *Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10 as to Instructional Quality*

	Instructional Quality	Respondents			
		Teachers		Experts	
		WM	VI	WM	VI
1.	Purpose of the material is well-defined.	4.00	VS	3.50	VS
2.	Material effectively stimulates the creativity of the target user.	3.90	VS	3.90	VS
3.	Learning objectives are clearly stated and measurable.	3.90	VS	3.95	VS
4.	Level of difficulty is appropriate for the intended target user.	3.90	VS	3.95	VS
5.	Graphics/colors/ sounds are used for appropriate instructional reasons.	3.76	VS	3.85	VS
6.	Material is enjoyable, stimulating, challenging, and engaging.	3.76	VS	3.80	VS
7.	Material effectively stimulates the creativity of the target user.	3.90	VS	3.95	VS
8.	Feedback on the target user's responses is effectively employed.	3.95	VS	3.90	VS
9.	Target users can control the rate and sequence of presentation and review.	3.90	VS	3.95	VS
10.	Instruction is integrated with the target user's previous experience.	3.90	VS	3.95	VS
Overall Weighted Mean		3.89	VS	3.87	VS

Table 3 illustrates that the Science teachers achieved a weighted mean of 3.89, and the experts scored 3.87, with standard deviations of 0.23 and 0.22, respectively. These results are verbally interpreted as Very Satisfactory.

The findings indicate a consensus among respondents regarding the demonstrated instructional quality of the developed Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10. The modules exhibit various commendable characteristics, including a well-defined purpose, successful achievement of defined objectives, clear and measurable learning goals, appropriate difficulty levels tailored for the target audience, judicious use of graphics/colors/sounds for instructional purposes, an enjoyable and stimulating presentation, a challenging and engaging nature, effective stimulation of the creativity of the target users, adept utilization of feedback on user responses, user-controlled pacing and sequencing of content, and integration of instruction with the target users' previous experiences.

The discovery in this research closely mirrors the findings reported in Adona's 2018 study. In Adona's study, the respondents demonstrated a high level of agreement when it came to assessing the instructional quality of the interactive web-based learning module developed for Science 7.

Table 4. Respondents' Evaluations on the Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10 as to Technical Quality

	Technical Quality	Respondents			
		Teachers		Experts	
		WM	VI	WM	VI
1.	Audio enhances understanding of the concept.	3.81	VS	3.95	VS
2.	Speech and narration (correct pacing, intonation, and pronunciation) is clear and can be easily understood.	3.86	VS	3.85	VS
3.	There is complete synchronization of audio with the visuals, if any.	3.86	VS	3.95	VS
4.	Music and sound effects are appropriate and effective for instructional purposes.	3.81	VS	4.00	VS
5.	Screen display (text) are uncluttered, easy to read, and aesthetically pleasing.	3.67	VS	4.00	VS
6.	Visual presentations (non-text) are clear and easy to interpret.	3.95	VS	3.95	VS
7.	Visuals sustain interest and do not distract user's attention.	3.81	VS	3.95	VS
8.	Visuals provide accurate representation of the concept discussed.	3.86	VS	3.70	VS
9.	The design allows the target user to navigate freely through the material.	3.86	VS	3.85	VS
10.	The material can easily and independently be used.	3.81	VS	3.95	VS
Overall Weighted Mean		3.83	VS	3.92	VS

Table 4 presents that the Science teachers achieved a weighted mean of 3.83, and the experts scored 3.92, accompanied by standard deviations of 0.28 and 0.17, respectively. These values are verbally interpreted as Very Satisfactory, indicating a high level of satisfaction with the technical aspects of the e-Learning Modules.

These findings suggest that the technical quality of the Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10 embodies several key characteristics. These include the enhancement of concept understanding through clear audio, precise speech, and narration with correct pacing, intonation, and pronunciation. Additionally, there is complete synchronization of audio with visuals, appropriate and effective use of music and sound effects for instructional purposes, uncluttered and aesthetically pleasing screen display of text, clear and easily interpretable non-text visual presentations, visuals that sustain interest without distracting the user, accurate representation of discussed concepts through visuals, a design allowing free navigation for the target user, and overall ease of independent use of the material.

This study aligns closely with the findings reported in Añonuevo's 2019 study. In Añonuevo's investigation, the participants exhibited a shared consensus in their evaluation of the developed intervention supplementary material, particularly in terms of its technical quality, where it was deemed acceptable.

Table 5. Respondents' Evaluations on the Developed Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10 as to Accuracy and Up-to-Datedness

	Accuracy and Up-to-Datedness	Respondents			
		Teachers		Experts	
		WM	VI	WM	VI
1.	The material does not contain conceptual error.	3.67	VS	3.65	VS
2.	The material does not contain factual error.	3.71	VS	3.75	VS
3.	Contents are relevant and timely.	3.90	VS	4.00	VS
4.	The material does not contain computational error.	3.81	VS	3.75	VS
5.	The material does not contain obsolete information.	3.86	VS	3.95	VS
Overall Weighted Mean		3.79	VS	3.82	VS

Table 5 displays that the Science teachers achieved a weighted mean of 3.79, and the experts scored 3.82, with standard deviations of 0.33 and 0.30, respectively. These values are verbally interpreted as Very Satisfactory, indicating a high level of satisfaction with the accuracy and currency of the e-Learning Modules.

The results indicate unanimous agreement among respondents that the materials demonstrated a very satisfactory level of accuracy and up-to-datedness. These findings suggest that the Accuracy and Up-to-Datedness of the Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10 possess the following characteristics: absence of conceptual, factual, and computational errors, and the contents are both relevant and timely.

This research closely corresponds to the results presented in Buitre's study from 2023. Buitre's exploration revealed a collective agreement among participants in assessing the created content, especially in terms of its Accuracy and Currency, both of which were deemed highly satisfactory.

Test of Significant Difference in the Evaluation of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10

Table 6. *Test of Significant Difference in the Evaluation of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10 in terms of Content Quality*

Respondents	n	OWM	s	Computed t-Value	Critical t-value	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	21	3.93	0.15	0.39	2.02	Fail to reject the H ₀	Not Significant
Experts	20	3.91	0.23				

As shown in Table 6, the calculated t value of 0.39 is lower than the critical t value of 2.02 at a significance level of 0.05 with 39 degrees of freedom. Therefore, based on statistical analysis, we do not reject the null hypothesis. This indicates that there is no significant difference between the evaluations provided by the two groups of respondents regarding the content quality of the developed Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10.

This indicates that the content quality of the developed Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10 is in harmony with DepEd Learning Competencies, facilitating enrichment, reinforcement, and mastery of learning objectives.

Table 7. *Test of Significant Difference in the Evaluation of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10 in terms of Instructional Quality*

Respondents	n	OWM	s	Computed t-Value	Critical t-value	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	21	3.89	0.23	0.29	2.02	Fail to reject the H ₀	Not Significant
Experts	20	3.87	0.22				

As shown in Table 7, the computed t value of 0.29 is less than the critical t value of 2.02. Therefore, at a 0.05 significance level, the statistical decision is to fail to reject the null hypothesis. Consequently, there is no significant difference in the evaluations provided by the two groups of respondents regarding the instructional quality of the developed Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10.

This suggests that the quality of instruction within the developed Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10 is evident through well-defined purpose, successful achievement of objectives, clear and measurable learning goals, suitable difficulty level, purposeful use of graphics/colors/sounds, enjoyable and engaging content, stimulation of creativity, effective use of feedback, and user control over presentation pace and sequence.

Table 8. *Test of Significant Difference in the Evaluation of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10 in terms of Technical Quality*

Respondents	n	OWM	s	Computed t-Value	Critical t-value	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	21	3.83	0.28	1.18	2.02	Fail to reject the H ₀	Not Significant
Experts	20	3.92	0.17				

As illustrated in Table 8, the calculated t value of 1.18 is below the critical t value of 2.02. At a 0.05 significance level, this indicates that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. This finding supports the conclusion that there is no significant difference between the evaluations provided by the two groups of respondents regarding the technical quality of the developed Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10.

This suggests that the technical quality of the developed Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10 includes features such as audio that aids comprehension with clear speech and narration, well-synchronized audio and visuals, judicious use of suitable music and sound effects, neat and readable screen text, visually engaging presentations without causing distraction, accurate representation of concepts through visuals, a user-friendly design allowing free navigation, and overall ease of independent use of the material.

Table 9. *Test of Significant Difference in the Evaluation of the Two Groups of Respondents on the Developed Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10 in terms of Accuracy and Up-to-Datedness*

Respondents	n	OWM	s	Computed t-Value	Critical t-value	Decision	Interpretation
Teachers	21	3.79	0.33	0.30	2.02	Fail to reject the H ₀	Not Significant
Experts	20	3.82	0.30				

The table demonstrates that the calculated t value of 0.30 is below the critical t value of 2.02. As a result, based on statistical analysis at a 0.05 level of significance, the decision is not to reject the null hypothesis. This implies that there is no noteworthy difference in how the two groups of respondents assessed the developed e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10 concerning accuracy and up-to-datedness.

This implies that the Accuracy and Up-to-Datedness of the developed Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10 is free from conceptual and factual errors, contains relevant and current content, lacks computational errors, and avoids obsolete information.

Level Performance of the Grade 10 Students Before and After Using the Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10

Table 10. Performance of the Grade 10 Students Before and After Using the Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10

Score	Descriptor	Pretest		Posttest	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
44 – 50	Highly Proficient	1	3.1	29	90.6
37 – 43	Proficient	1	3.1	2	6.3
25 – 36	Nearly Proficient	20	62.5	1	3.1
13 – 24	Low Proficient	10	31.3	0	0
00 – 12	Not Proficient	0	0	0	0
Total		32	100	32	100
Mean		28.34		48.16	
Standard Deviation		7.11		3.35	
Interpretation		Nearly Proficient		Highly Proficient	

It reveals that, on the pretest, 10 students, or 31.3%, scored under the category of low proficient, 20 students, or 62.5%, fell under nearly proficient, and 1 student, or 3.1%, achieved scores under proficient and highly proficient categories. On the posttest, 1 student, or 3.1%, scored under nearly proficient, 1 student, or 6.3%, under proficient, and 29 students, or 90.6%, scored under the highly proficient category.

Moreover, the pretest results, showing an average score of 28.34 and a standard deviation of 7.11, indicate a nearly proficient level of performance. In contrast, the posttest outcomes, demonstrating an average score of 48.16 and a standard deviation of 3.35, are considered highly proficient. This indicates a significant improvement in students' performance following the use of Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10.

Test of Significant Difference in the Mean Score of Grade 10 Students in the Pretest and Posttest

Table 11. Test of Significant Difference in the Pretest and Posttest Mean Scores

Respondents	Mean Score	s	Computed t-Value	Critical t-value	Decision	Interpretation
Pretest	28.34	7.11	14.19	2.08	Reject the H ₀	Significant
Posttest	48.16	3.35				

As per Table 11, the calculated t value of 14.19 surpasses the critical t value of 2.08 at a 0.05 level of significance with 31 degrees of freedom. Given this, the statistical decision is to reject the null hypothesis.

Therefore, there is enough evidence pointing towards a significant difference in the average scores of Grade 10 students between the pretest and posttest. This suggests that the implementation of the developed Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10 has proven to be successful in enhancing students' academic achievements.

Comments and Suggestions of the Teachers and Experts to Improve the Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10

Comments:

- 1 Activities are appropriate and suitable to attain the learning goals.
2. The learning materials are visually appealing and engaging.
3. The materials are timely and will undoubtedly assist online and modular students in understanding the concept
4. This e-Learning module is a good instructional material for students to independently learn the lessons. However, there are some parts which need to be improved. Some of the guide questions need to be revised.
5. The modules are very informative, and they serve their purpose.

Suggestions:

1. If possible, look for materials that are locally available or present at home so that most (If not all) of the presented activities in the e-learning module will be accomplished.
2. Specify what students need to observe to lead and guide them to effectively understand the concepts.

Conclusion

Based on the foregoing findings, the following conclusions were drawn: There were topics in Chemistry 10 that can be used in the development of contextualized e-learning modules. The developed Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10 were commendable to the Chemistry and Science teacher respondents and effective to use as learning resources in teaching Chemistry 10. The two groups of respondents concurred and agreed with the same ideas as they rated the developed Contextualized E-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10 with Very Satisfactory rating. The use of the Contextualized-Based e-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10 led to an enhanced performance among the student participants, facilitated by a variety of engaging activities incorporated into the e-Learning Modules. The developed Contextualized E-Learning Modules in Chemistry 10 contributed to significant improvement on the level of performance of its target users. The developed learning material could be further enhanced by incorporating the comments and suggestions of the two groups of respondents.

References

- Anclote, M. R (2017) Localized and Contextualized Learning Module in Science 8 (Chemistry) As Intervention Material (Master's Thesis), Marikina Polytechnic College, Marikina City.
- Adona, S. J (2018). Development and Validation of An Interactive Web-Based Learning Module in Science 7 (Master's Thesis), Marikina Polytechnic College, Marikina City.
- Agarwal, P. (2019). Importance Of Contextual Learning and Benefits to Learners | JBCN. JBCN International School. <https://www.jbcschool.edu.in/blog/importance-of-contextual-learning/>.
- Anonuevo, H. (2019). Interactive Supplementary Intervention Materials in Chemistry 8 (Master's Thesis), Marikina Polytechnic College, Marikina City.
- Armstrong, D., & Poë, J. C. (2020). The Science of Human Health—A Context-Based Chemistry Course for Non-Science Majors Incorporating Systems Thinking. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 97(11), 3957–3965. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jchemed.0c00887>
- Tomlinson, B., & Masuhara, H. (2004). Developing Language Course Materials.
- Buitre, S. L. (2023). Electronic Strategic Intervention (e-SIM) in Grade 7 (Biology): Effects on Students Performance (Master's Thesis), Marikina Polytechnic College, Marikina City.
- DepEd. (2019). DepEd Order No. 21, Series of 2019. Policy Guidelines on the K to 12 Basic. Retrieved from https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2019/08/DO_s2019_021.pdf.
- DepEd. (2020). DepEd Order No. 18, Series of 2020. Policy Guidelines for the Provision of Learning Resources in the Implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan. Retrieved from https://www.deped.gov.ph/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/DO_s2020_018.pdf.
- Majid, N., & Rohaeti, E. (2018). The Effect of Context-Based Chemistry Learning on Student Achievement and Attitude. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 6(6), 836–839. <https://doi.org/10.12691/education-6-6-37>.
- Pinuela, J. B. F (2022). Supplementary Digitalized Work Activities in Science 10 (Chemistry) For Enhancement of Student's Academic Performance (Master's Thesis), Marikina Polytechnic College, Marikina City.
- Pokhrel, S., & Chhetri, R. (2021). A Literature Review on Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic on Teaching and Learning. *Sage Journal*, 8(1). DOI: 10.1177/2347631120983481.
- Smith, J. K. (2018). Descriptive Research. In N. J. Salkind (Ed.), *Encyclopedia of Research Design* (Vol. 1, pp. 384-387). SAGE Publications. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781412961288.n120>.
- Suryawati, E., & Osman, K. (2017). Contextual Learning: Innovative Approach towards the Development of Students' Scientific Attitude and Natural Science Performance. *EURASIA Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 14(1). <https://doi.org/10.12973/ejmste/79329>

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